

Circular strategies to valorise seafood cooking waters into protein ingredients and microalgae nutrients

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Background/Problem

Seafood cooking processes generate large volumes of water rich in organic matter that is typically discarded, increasing treatment costs and environmental impact. Converting these waters into value-added products could bring significant economic and sustainability benefits for processors.

Practice Change

Treat cooking waters as a recoverable side-stream and process them using centrifugation + membrane filtration (ultrafiltration and nanofiltration) to create valuable outputs instead of sending the stream straight to wastewater treatment.

Evidence

Cooking waters from tuna and octopus processors in Galicia (Spain) were treated with centrifugation, ultrafiltration, and nanofiltration, producing: (1) high-protein retentates (up to 76% protein) suitable for aquafeeds/feed/food or further processing into bioactive peptides, and (2) permeates that showed promising results as a nutrient source for microalgae cultivation, reducing the need for freshwater and synthetic nutrients.

Setting/Participants

Seafood processing companies with regular, consistent generation of cooking-water streams (ideally from a single species to reduce variability), plus potential downstream users such as aquafeed/feed ingredient makers, fishmeal manufacturers, or microalgae producers.

Implementation Plan

Install a side-stream line that (1) centrifuges cooking water to remove solids, (2) applies ultrafiltration and nanofiltration to concentrate proteins and separate permeate, and (3) routes outputs to (a) protein-retentate handling (drying if viable, or shipping as a liquid concentrate) and (b) permeate reuse trials/scale-up for microalgae nutrients.

Outcomes/Measures

Protein content and usability of retentates; reduction in organic load sent to wastewater treatment; operational cost impacts for wastewater treatment; energy needs and feasibility of drying; and performance of permeate in microalgae cultivation (growth/yield) vs conventional nutrients.

Conclusion

Targeted centrifugation with membrane filtration can turn seafood cooking waters into two circular value streams, a high-protein ingredient and a reusable permeate, while reducing wastewater-treatment burden, with strongest feasibility where steady, single-species streams and sufficient volumes support downstream processing economics.

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Up to
76%
protein recovered
from tuna & octopus
cooking waters

fishmeal-comparable
product
(~USD 1,000/ton)
vs disposal routes

**Two value
streams**
from one "waste" stream